

Preparation and Characterisation of Trichloromono-(4-methoxyphenoxy)titanium(IV)

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In view of the emerging importance of aryloxide ligands in the field of organometallic chemistry related to metathesis¹, intra-molecular C-H activation via metallation of t-butyl groups of phenoxides² and isolation of hydrocarbon soluble compounds in low coordination states³, we have undertaken systematic investigations of some new metal aryloxides. In continuation to our report⁴ on the synthesis of tetrakis(4-methoxyphenoxy)titanium(IV), the present work describes the preparation and characterisation of trichloromono(4-methoxyphenoxy)titanium(IV), $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$ (**1**), and its reactivity with nitrogenous bases.

Results and Discussion

The formation of compound **1** may be rationalised in terms of the reaction,

Compound **1** is a moisture-sensitive dark red solid (m.p. 132°) and is soluble in chloroform, dichloromethane and carbon tetrachloride. Stoichiometric composition of the compound has been established by elemental analysis (Found : Ti, 17.02; Cl, 38.54; C, 30.34; H, 2.55. $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$ calcd. for : Ti, 17.26; Cl, 38.39; C, 30.28; H, 2.52%). Molar conductance value of the compound (10^{-3} M solution in nitrobenzene; $1.62 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggests it to be non-ionic while molecular weight determination indicates it to be monomer in this solvent.

Infrared spectrum of compound **1** shows no band in the region $3400-3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting the deprotonation of phenolic OH group which is substantiated by the actual evolution of hydrogen chloride gas during the reaction. The band at 1240 cm^{-1} in pure phenol is lowered by about 50 cm^{-1} which suggests a considerable contribution from a structure of the type $\text{C}=\overset{+\delta}{\text{O}}-\overset{-\delta}{\text{M}}$ resulting from drainage of electrons from the ring to the metal⁵. A new band around 575 cm^{-1} in the ir spectrum may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$ ⁶ while the bands at $385-410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{Ti-Cl}}$ modes. In the proton-nmr spectrum of **1**, two resonances observed at δ 3.60 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.62 (4H, s, ArH) in free phenol experience slight downfield shift which may be associated with the delocalisation of electrons from the aromatic nucleus to the titanium atom⁷.

In view of the better acceptor properties of titanium phenoxides than corresponding alkoxides⁸, the reactivity of **1** with nitrogenous bases has also been studied. The reaction of **1** with these bases are slightly exothermic and compounds of composition $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4).2\text{B}$ and $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4).\text{B}'$ are formed with monodentate (B) and bidentate (B') amines respectively (Table 1). These adducts are stable in dry atmosphere, non-electrolytes and exist as monomers in nitrobenzene as indicated by molecular weight determination.

Coordination from nitrogen of the bases to

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA OF TRICHLOROMONO(4-METHOXYPHENOXY)TITANIUM(IV) (I) AND ITS ADDUCTS WITH NITROGENOUS BASES

Compd./Colour	M. p. °C	Analysis % :		Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Mol. wt.* in PhNO_2 Found/(Calcd.)	$\nu_{\text{Ti-O}}$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_{\text{Ti-Cl}}$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_{\text{Ti-N}}$ cm^{-1}
		Found/(Calcd.)	Ti					
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$ (I) (Dark red)	132	17.02 (17.26)	38.54 (38.39)	1.62	275 (277)	575	385	—
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2-Dimethylamine (Maroon)	160d	11.35 (11.31)	24.82 (25.15)	1.68	—	570	395	282
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2-Triethylamine (Yellow)	158d	9.52 (9.99)	22.19 (22.21)	1.62	475 (479)	572	398	288
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2.n-Propylamine (Yellow)	>200	12.10 (12.11)	27.05 (26.93)	1.67	—	575	390	280
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2.n-Butylamine (Dark red)	134	11.52 (11.31)	25.13 (25.15)	1.63	421 (423)	570	410	290
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2-Diisopropylamine (Maroon)	106	9.78 (9.99)	22.20 (22.21)	1.67	—	572	390	282
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2.t-Butylamine (Light yellow)	148	10.82 (11.31)	24.83 (25.15)	1.68	426 (423)	570	392	288
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2,2'-Bipyridyl (Maroon)	>200	11.56 (11.75)	25.84 (26.14)	1.70	—	575	385	285
$\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.1,10-Phenanthroline (Yellow)	115	10.20 (10.07)	22.36 (22.41)	1.72	473 (475)	570	405	288

*Mean of three determinations.

titanium has been indicated by the appearance of new bands (not present in I) around $280\text{--}290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their ir spectra which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ti-N}}$ ⁹. Besides, the trend of shifts of bands due to ν_{NH} , $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{H-N-C}}$ deformations in aliphatic amines¹⁰ and those due to C=C, C=N and C-H out-of-plane deformations¹¹ on adduct formation, is in agreement with the earlier reports. Based upon the limited data available on these adducts, octahedral structure may be proposed for these adducts.

Experimental

Titanium(IV) chloride, 4-methoxyphenol and the solvents used were purified by the methods reported earlier. Proton-nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ir spectra (KBr/nujol) on a Beckmann spectrophotometer. Conductance studies were made on an Elico conductivity bridge while molecular weights were determined cryoscopically.

Compound 1 was synthesised by reacting TiCl_4 with 4-methoxyphenol in equimolar ratio in CCl_4

under reflux till evolution of HCl gas ceased. A red solid separated out when the resulting solution was concentrated and left overnight. The stoichiometric composition of the solid was established by elemental analysis. Addition compounds of composition $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.2B and $\text{TiCl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3-4)$.B' with monodentate (B) and bidentate (B') amines were prepared by reacting 1 with slight excess than calculated amounts of these amines in 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 ratio respectively, in CH_2Cl_2 under reflux. The solid adducts were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether and were dried under reduced pressure.

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NOTE

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